

A Study of a new Cyclohexylamine Chromithiocyanate Compound

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In an earlier communication¹ the formation of compounds between pyridine and methyl pyridines and potassium chromithiocyanate was discussed. We now report a new cyclohexylamine chromithiocyanate of composition $[C_6H_{11}NH_2]_2 Cr(SCN)_6 \cdot 2H_2O$. The structure was based on conductometric titrations and IR spectra.

Procedure—Potassium chromithiocyanate was prepared and standardised according to Roesler² and Bjerrum³. Pure cyclohexylamine (B.D.H.) was redistilled and a stock solution (M/10) was prepared in a 200-ml volumetric flask containing 5 ml of acetic acid (sp.gr. 1.05) at 25°. Solutions of different concentration were prepared by dilution with conductivity water.

Conductometric Study—The conductivity was measured by Philips Model PR 9500 instrument at 20°. Direct and indirect titration curves using equimolar solutions (M/10, M/50 and M/100), have been plotted after applying correction in Fig. 1. In case of direct titrations (curves 1, 2 and 3) the equivalent point is well pronounced when the solutions are strong but in reverse titrations (curves 4, 5 and 6) it is not so.

FIG. 1

1. Gupta and Anand, in press.
2. Roesler, *Annalen*, 1867, 141, 185.
3. Bjerrum, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1921, 118, 131; 1922, 199, 51.

Composition—The stoichiometry of the compound from cyclohexylamine and potassium chromithiocyanate is 3 : 1. The compound was obtained as pink precipitate in the above titrations. It was washed with water and dried in air and analysed { Found: SCN, 47.20; Cr, 7.00. $(C_6H_{11}.NH_2)_3 Cr(SCN)_3 \cdot 2H_2O$ requires SCN, 47.28; Cr, 7.06% }.

Solubility and Effect of Heat—The compound was found soluble partly in water and insoluble in dioxane. In ether it formed a heavier oily layer. It was highly soluble in methyl ethyl ketone, tri-*n*-butyl phosphate, *n*-butyl acetate and acetyl acetone. The compound when placed at 130° (the temp. raising gradually) in an oven, changed its colour to reddish-black and the whole of water of crystallisation was lost. But when placed in air it regained its colour and water {m.p. (anhydrous) 142° and 105° (hydrated)}.

IR Spectra—Spectra of potassium chromithiocyanate (curve 1) and cyclohexylamine chromithiocyanate (curve 2) by KBr-disc technique were obtained (Fig. 2). Characteristic frequencies of potassium chromithiocyanate and cyclohexyl chromithiocyanate are 2170 (s, SCN), 1650 (m, Cr-S) & 3600 (w, O-H) cm^{-1} and 2950 (s, NH_2^+), 3080 (s, CH), 2170 (s, SCN), 1650 (m, Cr-S), 1460 (s, HCH def.), 1380 (m, HCH def.) & 1000 (w, O-H def. in-plane) cm^{-1} respectively.

FIG. 2

In the octahedral $Cr(SCN)_6^{-3}$ ion SCN stretch, SCN wag, Cr-S stretch and S-Cr-S bend may be the possible modes of vibration in IR spectra. All vibrations belonging to the same symmetry class can mix with one another. In comparing IR spectra of potassium chromithiocyanate and cyclohexylamine chromithiocyanate it is evident that the symmetry of $Cr(SCN)_6^{-3}$ is still preserved in cyclohexylamine-chromithiocyanate even after replacing K by cyclohexylamine.

The author is thankful to the CDRI, Lucknow for providing IR spectra and to the Professor of Chemistry for providing research facilities and encouragement.